
Research Article

Feasibility Study of Jaffi Waterfalls as Source of Power Generation for the Communities within and around Kwaya-kusar Locality, Borno – Nigeria

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Abstract

This feasibility work presents the prospect of Jaffi waterfalls in Kwaya-kusar Area of Borno, Nigeria as a source of power generation using the micro-hydro generating system. The main aim is to analyze the data collected at the waterfalls site in order to conceptualize for the development of power generating system that could be feasible and reliable to the immediate communities. The major parameter that is significant for the design analysis here is the volume flow-rate, V , which was measured using the float and meter stick method at the water falls site. Also of concern is the height of the waterfall and 15.4 m was seen as the baseline limit, which is adequate for the analysis. The Microsoft Excel was chosen for the analysis, which was based on its flexibility and availability, is also shown to be widely used application tools used in interpreting similar data. The investigation carried out depicts that the waterfall of 15.4 m height that could produce a flow-rate of 0.74 m³/s maximum, is sufficient to generate electricity of up to 100 kW. This amount of electricity could be adequate enough to improve on the living standard of Ghuba community of Kwaya-kusar, hence with the installation problems of the power generating plant, migration to the city areas is expected to be reduced.

Keyword: Micro-hydro, development, flow-rate, height, investigation, electricity, installation.

Received: 12/04/19

Accepted: 09/06/19

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ISSN: 2141 - 4068 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Introduction

Energy is one of the most fundamental resources for world's growth and should be sourced using adequate engineering skills and mechanisms. Currently, Nigeria is facing numerous energy challenges at both domestic and industrial levels, which could be based on poor energy harvesting techniques from typical sources of energy available in the country. The electricity demand in Nigeria far outstrips the supply, which is nowadays epileptic in nature. These major predicaments and the poor state of power supply have been shown to be the actual set back of the country's under development (Aliyu, 1999). The country is blessed with numerous renewable and non-renewable energy resources, but still generating less than 5×10^3 MW and is below the country's population demand. The application of hydropower systems to harness and generate substantial electric power could be the steps towards adequate solution and at low cost. Also, the techniques applied to generate power are expected to be environmentally friendly systems, which could assist in boosting the present day national grid supply and are helpful to the development of the immediate rural communities. Nigeria has large hydropower potentials of over 14.7×10^3 MW (Olayinka *et al.*, 2010) which has not been optimally utilized and currently, only about 1.9×10^3 MW could be utilized, which is obviously inadequate for the present demand requirements. Their evaluation of the small hydropower technology as emphasized could be at a low level as compared with the scheme operated in only three states of the federation, which obviously should be unacceptable for meaningful development.

Electricity plays an important role in human daily life and the demand is increasing day by day with increased population and industrial development, as currently most of the household appliances are replaced with mechanized robots or machines (Rahman *et al.*, 2017). According to Sambo, (2008), electricity plays a very important role in the socio-economic and technological development of every nation. In the last decade world over, crisis such as oil shortage with risen cost, climate change, electricity demand with shortage of supply and restrictions of whole sale markets have been in the risen problems of energy boost (Sambo, 2008). These crucial energy situations have made it a necessity for alternative sources of generating electric power that the present investigation is concentrating. Also, the contributions of renewable energy: wind, solar, hydro, biofuels, etc., which have been used all over the world to generate electricity were still inadequate with only about 213 tetra Watt-hours of supply (World Energy, 2016). These typical alternative sources have lesser effects on the environment (e.g. pollution), even though the cost of generation depends on the energy sources and conversion technology.

Hydro-electric power is a form of renewable energy resource, which comes from flowing water that must be in motion and could generate electricity. When the water is falling by the force of gravity, its potential energy converts into kinetic energy which turns the turbine blades or vanes in a hydraulic turbine and finally changes to mechanical energy. Also, as the turbine turns the generator rotor, it converts the mechanical energy to electrical energy (Robert and Bailey, 2009), but this type of power plants requires high potential energy head to run the turbine (Yah *et al.*, 2017). Elie *et al.*, (2017) carried out a detailed methodology of feasibility studies of micro-hydropower plants in Cameroon: case study of the micro-hydro of KEMKEN. The study was supported by feasibility studies of KEMKEN MHPP project of 320 kW installed power, where Kaplan turbine was recommended. The most well-known method of generating electricity from hydro power is by creating an artificial lake and develops it into large Dam in a River pathway. The environmental benefit of this type of hydropower plant is significant and therefore eases construction (Benchimal and Peres, 2015, Fearnside, 2016, Palmeririn *et al.*, 2015). Energy can be stored in battery banks at sites that are far from a facility or used in addition to a system that is directly connected, therefore in times of high demand there is additional reserve energy available (Fegbohun, 2015).

Potentials of Hydropower in Nigeria

To support economic growth and development, electric power must be in abundance, even though for Nigeria the generation capacity is far short of the required demand of 10^4 MW (Okpanefe and Owolobi, 2002, Fagbohun and Adebajji, 2002). Worthy of note is that as at 2015, the electricity generation in Nigeria ranges between 4.5×10^3 MW - 6.5×10^3 MW (Okpanefe and Owolobi, 2002). Currently, the country's electricity generation utility now unbundled from government finance to private ones (Okpanefe and Owolobi, 2002, Omotoso and Aribisala, 2008) and those companies are still unable to cope with the electricity demands. The demand in electricity is growing to an average of 1 % annually, with about 65 % of the rural populace lacking access to the ordinary conventional electric power (Omotoso and Aribisala, 2008).

Estimates of 736 MW of electric energy from hydropower been shown obtainable from small rivers and swift flowing streams in Nigeria (Ramakumar, 2014, Essan, 2007) and the potentials are obvious if harnessed (Durman and Gokcol, 2011, David, 2013). A viability study shows that three hydro stations at Makurdi, Lokoja and Ikom could also add up to certain amount of power to the national grid. In addition to these sites, there are number of identified sites with the potentials for supporting micro hydro (< 100 kW) and mini hydro (ranges from 500 - 5,000 kW) power systems in Nigeria with over 248 small rivers shown. Olumuyiwa *et al.* (2015) carried out a detailed small hydropower

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ISSN: 2141 - 4068 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

viability assessment of river Eleme in Ekiti State of Nigeria, their result showed that the head of the river is 8 m with an average minimum and maximum discharge of 9.1 m³/s and 82.5 m³/s, respectively. They also showed that an average power of 2.21 MW could be generated with an optimum operating period of 183 days per annum.

The country's energy consumption statistics indicates that hydropower covers up to 23.9 % as at 2007 and was 14.2 % in 2003 (Essan, 2007), which shows that there is good level of improvement in this sector. Technically, hydropower potential is put at 20,000 MW, even though hypothetically approximated potential is about 30,000 MW (NASENI, 2011). Currently, the main hydro sites are at Kainji and Jebba on the river Niger and Shiroro on the Kaduna River, with generating capacity of 760 (Daily Trust, 2012), 540 (Fagbohun, 2015, MESL, 2009) and 600 MW (SIC, 2009), respectively. Small-scale hydro schemes also exists in Jos, Plateau State, it generates and supplies about 19 MW and is licensed to a private sector: National Electricity Supply Company (NESCO); the Mambila hydropower is also expected to be completed and could generate over 5,000 MW.

This work concentrates on the how best hydropower energy source could be harnessed and utilized within a local community that has the required sources. The present research investigation is initially carrying out a feasibility work of the Jaffi waterfalls located at Kwaya-kusar local community, in order to generate electric power using micro hydro turbine system. The main objectives are to collect and analyze data of annual rainfall of the locality, to determine the minimum and maximum volume flow rate of the water falls and to estimate the possible power that can be generated from the water falls.

Materials and method

The Study Site and its Geographical Location

Kwaya-kusar has an area of 732 km² and a population of 56.5 thousand as at the 2006 census with its inhabitant speaking majorly Bura and sparsely Tera tribes. The people of Kwaya-kusar are largely subsistence farmers, as sourced by the United Nation Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (NGO Relief web - Map, 2018) It shows that most of the communities that covers the Kwaya-kusar area have not been privileged with adequate electric power supply, which this work attempt to proffer solution. The Jaffi waterfall is situated within latitude 10°30'11 N and longitude 11°50'36 E of Kwaya-kusar Area of Borno State, Nigeria. It drops from a Plateau of 15.4 m height and into a Valley, the water flows throughout the year and has a solitary and pleasant environment which is ideal for excursion and other related field trips (FGN, 2000).

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ISSN: 2141 - 4068 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

The present work feasibility studies were carried out between September 2017 to August 2018 and it includes: data collection based on measurements, interviews with the local people and analysis of the data collected. The Author's field Survey, in the 2018 showed that in its outlook and water strength, the waterfall varies during dry and rainy seasons as Plates 1 and 2 show. Plate 1 shows that the rocks around the waterfall could be dark brownish and with the waterfalls.

Plate 1: Jaffi water fall in dry season

Plate 2: Jaffi water fall in rainy season

converging down the stream, while plate 2 shows that the waterfall diverges down the stream with the rocks showing greenish characteristics, although both could be adequate. This indicates that during the rainy season, the amount and strength of water could be higher and with better expectations for high efficiency of the machine. Even though, operating the machine during this period could be at risk, which is based on unforeseeable problems attributed to raining season and therefore the design must be able to overcome such critical problems.

Measurement of the Head and the Flow Rate

The energy available in the water is a function of two variables: the head and the flow rate (Gaffe and Kadhim, 2012). The head is the vertical distance through which the water can be made to fall, is typically measured in units of meters (or feet). The flow-rate is the quantity of water moving past a fixed point in a given time and is measured in cubic meter (or cubic feet per second (CFS) or gallons per second (GPS) - usually not in use now). Both head and flow-rate contribute equally to the energy of the waterfalls: the greater the volume of water, the higher it is in height and the more energy it can contains.

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Noting that small stream with large vertical water drops supplies the same amount of energy as much larger stream with a very slight drops.

The flow rate can either be measured or estimated directly; therefore in either case, the hydrology should be based on many years of a daily record (Harvey, 2006). Typically, for short duration investigation, the area rainfall methods are preferable, because historic precipitin data is relatively easy to obtain. It is always a good idea however, to take periodic site measurements if possible, to verify that the results of the analysis are accurate. Data on rainfall in the proposed Pico/micro - hydro station area were collected for six years from Nigeria Metrological Centre, Biu zonal office, Borno State. These data spans through the year 2011 to 2016, with a peak rainfall of 1.08×10^3 mm in 2016. The elevation of Jaffi waterfalls was measured as 15.4 m and the flow rate of water fall was measured using a float and a meter stick techniques with a friction correction factor of 0.85 (Harrelson *et al.*, (1994).

Theoretical Power for a Hydro System

For an ideal hydro system (Gabriel, 2015), the expected maximum theoretical power is related to the flow rate and the head, which is developed based on Equations 1 - 4 and shown as Equations 5 - 6. Equation 1 shows that acceleration due to free waterfalls, g (m/s^2) is related to the mass and head of the waterfall, then potential energy, E_p of the water at that altitude is as in the Equation. Also, since the density ρ , of the water is the ratio of the mass to the volume, V , then Equation 2 influences the power in the waterfall. Equations 1 and 2 then changes to Equations 3, 4 or 5 as shown and are further converted to Equations 6 or 7 as potential power expected from the water.

$$E_p = mgh \quad (1)$$

$$\rho = \frac{m}{V} \quad (2)$$

$$E_p = \rho Vgh \quad (3)$$

$$E_p = \frac{1000Vgh}{t} \quad (4)$$

$$P = 1000Qgh \quad (5)$$

$$P = 1000^ng hQ \quad (6)$$

$$P = 9.81 \times Q \times h \quad (7)$$

Where P is the potential power in kW, Q is the flow rate in m^3/s and h is the head in m and η is the experimental exponent. The nonlinear relationship of the mechanical power of a turbine is expressed in Equation 6 (Sattou, 2014 and Bhoi and Ali, 2014). Noting that when both the head and the flow rate data were measured and obtained, the potential power was also obtained (Bala, 2010) using Equation 7.

Results and Discussion

Effects of Rainfall on Waterfalls

The average values of the flow rate were calculated for each month during the dry and rainy seasons: that is from November to March and from April to October, respectively. The power that could be generated was calculated using the peak values obtained for each month as shown in Figure 1 for the rainy season. Figure 2 depicts the average flow-rate of the waterfall during the periods under observation, which were based on the measured daily data. The minimum average value of the flow rate is $0.37 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and it was during the dry season and a maximum value of $0.74 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ was shown during the rainy period. This shows that waterfalls increases from dry season and reaches its peak in the rainy period, as in Figure 1 and then declined at the concluding stage, which indicates that the quantum of waterfall is proportional to the rainfall.

Influence of Flow Rate on Power and the Waterfalls

It is the interaction and combination of head and the flow rate that results into power, which is expected hence the development and utilization of the machine. For this reason, Jaffi waterfalls, with its impressive vertical drops can potentially generate useful amounts of power using relatively small volumes of water. Figure 3 shows that the trend of the power expected during the period of both dry and rainy season is similar to the flow rate hence is also proportional to it. The maximum power to be generated is 100 kW and is during the month of August as shown in the Figure 3, as this month is normally the peak in rainy season.

Figure 1: The 2011-2016 monthly average rainfall of Kwaya-kusar area

Figure 2: Monthly variation of flow-rate based on the strength of the waterfall

Table 1: Domestic Loads Sizing Requirement

S/ N	Items	Quantity	Unit (W)	load Number	of Household	Total (kW)	Load
1	Lighting	4	15	66		3.96	
2	Fans	2	45	66		5.94	
3	Mobile charging	2	10	66		1.32	
4	Refrigerator	1	445	7		3.12	
5	TV set	1	40	45		1.80	
6	Satellite dish	1	30	13		0.39	
Total						16.53	

Figure 3: Monthly variation of expected power output based on the strength of the waterfall

Table 2: Public Building (Dispensary) Energy Requirement

S/N	Items	Quantity	Unit (W)	Load	Total (kW)	Load
1	Fan	7	45		0.32	
2	Lighting	8	15		0.12	
3	Tv set	1	40		0.04	
4	Refrigerator	1	445		0.45	
5	3870 HSG-WS Sterilizer model	1	3500		9.00	
Total					9.93	

Public lighting load: 20 numbers of street light = $20 \times 18 = 0.36$ kW
Assuming the future load growth to be 10%

$$\Rightarrow \text{Future growth load} = 0.1 (\text{domestic load} + \text{public lighting} + \text{public building load}) \\ = 0.1 (16.53 + 0.36 + 9.53) = 2.64 \text{ kW}$$

Total Energy requirement of the rural community = $16.53 + 0.36 + 9.52 + 2.64 = 29.05$ kW

The Requirement for Energy Demand

The need for energy utilization at certain rural areas is mostly for domestic consumption, which also depends on the dimension of the area. The level of sophistication of consumers and their equipment determines the amount of energy applicable for use, as such rate of consumption in the rural community is relatively low as Tables 1 and 2 showed. Normally the use of electric power for cooking purpose is usually rare as woodpiles are traditionally and largely adopted. Hence as Tables 1 and 2 shows electricity are mainly for used in lightings, radio/TV applications, cellphone charging, ironing cloth, boiling hot water using electric kettle or ring, fan applications etc.

Conclusion

The feasibility analysis carried out and based on the data measured and obtained, showed that for certain month periods, average annual rainfall were minimum and maximum of 31 mm and 255 mm, respectively.

The result indicates that for a head of 15 m, minimum and maximum flow rates of 0.37 m³/s and 0.74 m³/s can generate electric power of up to 100 kW. The energy requirement of the rural community based on preliminary survey with the local people and authorities was calculated to be 29.05 kW.

The feasibility studies show that the living standards of communities within the area of operation of the micro hydropower machine will be improved, migration of rural dwellers to the city could be reduced and tourism could be attracted after such installation.

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